

Binary Classifier for Fault Detection Based on KDE and PCA

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Abstract—Fault detection in process condition monitoring aims to declare anomalies strayed from the operation expectancy. With the number of variables increasing, the complexity of detection task grows quickly. The algorithm, Binary Classifier for Fault Detection (BaFFle), is devised to employ Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce the number of variables and to detect the occurrences of fault over each distinct component using corresponding operation model. In this way, BaFFle converts a multivariate detection task into several univariate problems. Since the observations of a steady-state system are supposed to subject to certain probability distribution, the normal operation model is represented by probability distribution. In the original BaFFle algorithm, measured data of Gaussian distribution is assumed. In order to get rid of the strong assumption in BaFFle, an improved BaFFle is proposed in this paper to estimate the distribution model by Kernel Density Estimation (KDE). A main advance of KDE is attributed to the non-parametric way of estimating distribution, leading to a data determined estimator. Experiments using real industrial data proved the validation of KDE-based BaFFle. From the practice perspective, BaFFle has the potential of being applied to operation systems with non-Gaussian distributions.

Index Terms—binary classifier for fault detection (BaFFle), kernel density estimation (KDE), principal component analysis (PCA), process condition monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Fault detection plays a vital role in industrial process condition monitoring, aiming to perform online assessment of system health and provide efficient and sustainable operation process. Besides, fault detection serves related diagnosis and prognosis.

The paper [1] proposed an anomaly detection algorithm for stationary systems, Binary Classifier for Fault Detection (BaFFle), which is designed on the basis of Gaussian distribution assumption and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). PCA is an extensively used feature extraction method, being capable of linear dimension reduction; also, the distinct components obtained by PCA are linear uncorrelated, providing the feasibility to study system behaviours on each individual component. In this way, multivariate process can be simplified to a number of univariate processes and the fault detection at each time instant is determined jointly by principle components. However, the assumed Gaussian model for observations constrains the applications; a suitable statistic

model estimation is urging to enable BaFFle algorithm to fit into various operation processes.

Statistic model estimation is generally divided into two categories, respectively parametric and non-parametric methods. Parametric estimation aims to make an assumption of underlying model with finite parameters. In [2], the author reviewed a number of likelihood-based parametric estimation methods, such as a closed-form method to approximate likelihood [3] and quasi-maximum likelihood [4], [5]. However, the accuracy and precision of parametric estimation are heavily dependent on the correct model assumption, which has been a big challenge.

Comparing with parametric methods, nonparametric estimation takes advantage of model free to directly manipulate on measured data. Getting rid of model selection significantly improve the accuracy of statistical model estimation. To this end, one powerful and efficient nonparametric method named Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) is proposed and developed in the work of [6], [7]. KDE is able to automatically and flexibly generate distribution model, especially outperforming in solving complicated distribution issue.

This paper focuses on improving BaFFle algorithm using KDE instead of assuming Gaussian distribution, thereby generalising the BaFFle algorithm, and further exploring the potential of improving the fault detection accuracy. There are three main contributions in this paper:

- 1) apply KDE to BaFFle algorithm in order to estimate probability distribution in a non-parametric way
- 2) estimate and locate confidence interval using Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) and
- 3) validate KDE-based BaFFle on datasets collected from a real multiphase flow facility of Cranfield University, and make a comparison between KDE-based BaFFle and Gaussian-based BaFFle.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II provides a brief introduction of original BaFFle algorithm and elaborates on how to generalise BaFFle algorithm using KDE. Next, section III introduces the Cranfield datasets and the experiment settings for validating algorithm, and analyses the experiment results. Last part concludes the performance of the improved BaFFle algorithm.

II. METHODOLOGY

The original BaFFle algorithm proposed in [1] is devised for fault detection of stationary system. There are three main steps involved in BaFFle, respectively, initialisation, classification and model updating. Different from traditional fault detection, the normal operating model in BaFFle is trained from a very beginning segment of test system instead of from collected data in advance; in addition, there are two sets of monitoring control limits, one for alarming the emergence of suspicious fault and one for confirming the occurrences of fault; the distribution model and control limits are updated along the time.

A. PCA feature extraction

A time-series of measurements is denoted as X_1, X_2, \dots, X_t , where $X_t = [x_1^t, x_2^t, \dots, x_n^t]$ represents an n -dimension vector of observations at time instance t . To deal with multivariate problems, PCA is applied to extract features (or saying principal components) from raw process data to feed in detection algorithm. The motive of this manipulation is considering the advances of PCA in minimising the linear correlations between variables and maximising the information contained in distinct principal components. In practice, PCA provides a simple forward mapping from high dimension to lower dimension space.

In Baffle algorithm, the training set is a small dataset of length l captured from the running system, denoted as $B = [X_1, X_2, \dots, X_l] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times l}$. The dimension reduction of training data from n to r dimension space is

$$V = B^T Q \quad (1)$$

where B is the max-min scaled observations; $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ is the projection matrix obtained from B and $V \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times r}$ is the training data after dimension reduction.

The number of distinct principal components depends on the percentage of total variance explained. According to the cut-off rule in [8], the remained principal components are supposed to account for 70 % of total variance. In this way, the number of components is automatically determined, differing from datasets to datasets.

Starting from time stamp $l + 1$, the observations through dimension reduction projection are

$$Y_t = X_t^T Q \quad (2)$$

where $Y_t = [y_t^1, y_t^2, \dots, y_t^r]$ is the X_t in r -dimension space at time t .

B. Kernel density estimation

Probability distribution is used for representing operation model in BaFFle algorithm. Originally, an extensively used distribution, Gaussian model, is assumed to describe the statistical distribution of process data. However, this assumption lacks in handling the uncertainty of density model. Hence, a non-parameter method, Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), is employed to sidestep model selection issue.

Next, we continue this section taking the component of the r -th dimension y^r to explain KDE. According to [9], the probability of y^r is given by

$$p(y^r) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{i=1}^n K\left(\frac{y^r - y_i^r}{h}\right) \quad (3)$$

where n is the sample size, h is the bandwidth, y_i^r represents the i -th sample of y_i^r and $k(\cdot)$ is the kernel function. The overall performance of the kernel density estimator is associated with the selection of bandwidth and the type of kernel function. Reference [10] illustrates that an excessively small value of h produces wiggles on the plot of KDE, whereas a large h yields oversmoothed plot; hence, the determination of a proper h is essential to smooth the distribution curve. In [11], an approximation method of optimal bandwidth h is offered to satisfy the objective of minimising the mean integrated square error, having:

$$h_{opt} = 1.06\sigma^{-\frac{1}{5}} \quad (4)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of principle component. Besides, kernel function selection is discussed in [11] and [12], remarking that the estimation error has small differences between commonly used kernel functions, such as Gaussian kernel, Epanechnikov kernel and Triweight kernel. In this sense, Gaussian kernel is used and given by

$$K(g) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}g^2} \quad (5)$$

C. Monitoring thresholds and binary classification

BaFFle algorithm in [1] performed an adaptive monitoring threshold strategy, in which the monitoring limit takes on a 3σ distance away from the mean of a Gaussian model to warn the occurrence of suspect fault and to tune the parameter $k \in (0, 1)$ of another monitoring threshold, $m \pm (k+3)\sigma$, which is adopted to evaluate the system status again with higher standard, increasing the confidence of confirming the occurrence of fault. A same idea is applied in KDE-based BaFFle. Due to the absence of a specific model assumption, confidence interval of an unknown distribution will be calculated through CDF. Probabilities relating to the confidence interval under PDF is:

$$P(a \leq X \leq b) = \int_a^b p(x^r) dx^r = P(b) - P(a) \quad (6)$$

where

$$p(x^r) = \int_{-\infty}^{x^r} p(u) du \quad (7)$$

is the CDF. Then the lower and upper endpoints of confidence interval are settled at a and b . The confidence levels in KDE based BaFFle are 99.73 % and 99.99 % corresponding to 3σ and 4σ deviation of Gaussian distribution in the original BaFFle. The confidence intervals of the improved BaFFle are respectively written as $ConInt_1 = (a_1, b_1)$ and $ConInt_2 = (a_2, b_2)$. Note that the confidence level of $ConInt_2$ varies according to the detection results with confidence level 99.73%. Any y_t^r that cannot fall into the confidence area is declared as abnormal event [1]. Detailed fault detection is as follows:

$$W_t^r = \begin{cases} 1 & , y_t^r < a_1 \text{ or } y_t^r > b_1 \\ 0 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$E_t^r = \begin{cases} 1 & , y_t^r < a_2 \text{ or } y_t^r > b_2 \\ 0 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where W_t^r and E_t^r represent the detection results according to the control limits $ConInt_1$ and $ConInt_2$ on r -th component. Value 1 indicates that there exists fault in the system, whereas 0 is non-fault. If over half components alert fault happening in the system, the evaluation of system status at time t is unhealthy.

In addition, the acquisition of probability distribution is a continuously learning process rather than a one-time learning. Newly collected data will be taken into a new round of probability distribution estimation; meanwhile, the oldest data will be abandoned. In this way, probability distribution of observations is updated at each time instant. Considering the possibility of false negative, probability estimation may only use a portion of the full value of observations. In this way, samples for KDE are filtered. Since there are three combinations of the results of E_t^r and W_t^r , an averaging filter considering three kinds of situations is formulated. Eq. 10 gives the details:

$$\hat{y}_t^r = \begin{cases} \alpha y_t^r + (1 - \alpha) \hat{y}_{t-1}^r, & \text{if } E_t^r = 0, W_t^r = 0 \\ \alpha y_t^r + (1 - \alpha) b^r, & \text{if } E_t^r = 0, W_t^r = 1 \\ b^r, & \text{if } E_t^r = 1, W_t^r = 1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $b^r \in \{x_1^r, x_2^r, \dots, x_l^r\}$, \hat{y}_t^r is the processed y_t^r , and α is the influence factor, $\in [0, 1]$.

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

This section presents the application of KDE-based BaFFle on the real industrial datasets, and compares the results of KDE-based and Gaussian-based BaFFle.

A. Experiment description

The datasets used in this experiment are collected and published by the lab of Cranfield University. Cranfield researchers built up a three-phase flow facility to simulate the process of air-liquid mixture; and six types of fault operations are designed. The sketch and description of the multiphase flow rig can be found in [9].

TABLE I

OPERATION DETAILS FOR DATASETS AND THE NUMBER OF RESERVED PRICIPAL COMPONENTS, SAMPLING RATE=1HZ

Fault Type	Datesets	Duration (s)	Fault Start (s)	Fault End (s)	Remained Dimensions
A	1-1	4467	657	3777	3
	1-2	4321	691	3691	2
B	2-1	3496	476	2656	4
	2-2	3421	331	2467	3
C	3-1	6272	333	5871	3
	3-2	10764	596	9566	4
D	4-1	4451	851	3851	4
	4-2	3661	241	3241	4

Since this paper focuses on detecting the changes from normal condition to abnormal condition, we select the datasets obtained under steady-state operation to validate KDE-based BaFFle. These datasets include four types of faults: air line blockage (type A), water line blockage (type B), top separator input blockage (type C) and open direct bypass (type D). Table I summarized the details of datasets, including the fault duration, the time of fault start and end and the number of reserved principal components. To fairly compare the performance of the improved algorithm and original BaFFle, the parameters of KDE-based BaFFle are consistent with the settings in [1]: the sample size for estimating probability distribution is $l = 150$; the number of reserved dimensions is according to 70% cut-off rule of the cumulative variance; impact factor α equals to 0.5.

B. Experiment Results

Firstly, we explored the differences of probability distribution obtained via Gaussian model and KDE. Fig. 1 displays the distribution plots of dataset 3-2: real line presenting the distribution curve based on KDE and dotted line presenting Gaussian distribution. As shown in the Fig. 1, KDE gives a skewed bimodal curve; however, Gaussian distribution as known is a symmetric ‘bell’ shape. Additionally, there are obvious differences between two curves particularly in terms of the number of modality; the distribution provided by KDE is bimodal. On the other hand, two distribution plots are gradually getting closely at the tail parts. Through the comparison, KDE is a suitable tool to precisely reflect the distribution of data.

Fig. 1. Probability distribution plots for the first distinct principal component of dataset 3-2.

To measure the detection performance, three metrics which are Accuracy (ACC), Precision (PR) and Detection Time (DT) mentioned in [1], plus Detection Rate (DR) and Wrong Detection Rate (WDR) are employed in this paper to measure the performance of KDE-based fault detection. Two newly introduced metrics are used to have a further understanding of the revised BaFFle. DR calculates the percentage of true

TABLE II
EXPERIMENT RESULTS FOR EACH DATASET

Datasets	1-1		1-2		2-1		2-2		3-1		3-2		4-1		4-2	
	△	○	△	○	△	○	△	○	△	○	△	○	△	○	△	○
ACC (%)	27.75	27.73	39.25	39.18	43.16	42.34	51.7	51.82	68.28	68.34	95.74	97.71	81.05	81.24	86.16	87.7
PR (%)	50.07	50.04	88.6	89.73	81.63	80.85	91.26	91.31	98.6	98.86	96.31	98.58	84.35	84.61	93.92	95.73
DT (s)	2429	2429	2432	2432	177	1835	1511	1290	1888	1894	107	107	317	319	312	312
DR (%)	22.18	22.02	17.86	17.47	16.51	14.91	28.83	29.03	65.88	65.78	98.74	98.73	89.44	89.40	89.63	89.63
WDR (%)	100	99.42	11.09	9.67	9.75	9.27	6.28	6.23	13.18	10.7	28.36	10.76	83.03	81.36	41.57	28.74

△ represents KDE based BaFFle; ○ represents BaFFle

positives during the period of faults happening while WDR measures the false positives after fault end.

Table II shows the detection results for each dataset applied with two versions of BaFFle. From the aspects of DT and DR, abnormal operations in most cases can be slightly earlier detected using KDE-based method. Consequently, there is supposed to have an increase in the ACC and PR. However, the performances of ACC and PR are inconsistent with DR, showing slight drops in most datasets. Here, we use WDR to explain the conflict results.

Taking dataset 3 – 1 as an example, DT is reduced from 1894 (s) to 1888 (s), respectively the results of BaFFle and KDE-based BaFFle; meanwhile, DR performs an increase, from 65.78 % to 65.88%. The improvements in both DT and DR metrics prove that the new BaFFle algorithm is able to earlier detect the occurrences of fault than the original one and performs properly before fault end. Nevertheless, the drops in ACC and PR indicate that there are increasing incorrect detection by KDE-based BaFFle. The calculation of WDR shows that in KDE-based BaFFle algorithm, false positive after removing fault increases 2.48%, which can also be seen from the plots in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Plots of fault detection results of dataset 3-1. There are five detection results, including three sub-results identified by the first, second and third principal component, two final results respectively for KDE-based BaFFle and the original BaFFle.

Above, we can see that the wrong detection after removing abnormal operations has great influence on ACC and PR. The reason is because after abnormal behaviours are fixed, the operation is hard to back on the anticipated working condition as same as the initial phase, which is usual in industrial systems. In addition, as more precisely the probability distribution estimated, the differences between past and current behaviours become more obviously, causing the false positives rising up. In practice, the increase in false positives after fault removal can be neglected since the system will be forced to stop while fault is detected. Then after fixing the fault, BaFFle will treat the system as a new one and re-build the operating model.

IV. CONCLUSION

BaFFle is a fault detection algorithm proposed in [1]. This algorithm is able to quickly adapt into new work environments and conduct real-time process condition monitoring. However, the Gaussian distribution assumption in BaFFle constraints the system model type. Thus, this paper aims to provide a solution to bypassing the model selection issue, thereby making BaFFle algorithm be suitable to various systems. KDE is a model-free estimation tool that is capable of flexibly dealing with complicated system.

Through experiments, we find that KDE-based BaFFle is superior to the original BaFFle algorithm. Firstly, the improved BaFFle can estimate the probability distribution much closer to the real distribution at the absence of model specification. Secondly, the experiment results show that KDE-based BaFFle has the potential to improve the fault detection accuracy. But, there are still having some aspects to work on in the future study. KDE-based BaFFle works well on recognising abnormal operations while the condition of a system changes from healthy status to unhealthy status; nevertheless, detection system is unable to quickly react to the end-up-fault behaviour, causing a period of false positives after removing fault. There are two reasons to explain this phenomenon: the first is because BaFFle has a long memory of data that are stored during fault happening; the second is because a system that experienced abnormal operations need a period of time to recover to the healthy status.

To sum up, two aspects will be included in the future study. One is to solve the memory problem to reduce the influence from old data. Another one is to research on how to recognize the transition from abnormal process to normal one. The

transition process recognition would be helpful with expanding KDE-based BaFFle onto monitor varying-state system.

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